

Annex 4. SOIL DATA SHARING TEMPLATE TOWARDS JRC ESDAC BASED ON THE INSPIRE DIRECTIVE

1. This AGREEMENT is made

the (DATE)..... between

1. THE DG-JRC (name, direction, country, postal code, website, any other useful information to identify) represented for the purpose of signing this contract by (name, surname, email address)

and

2. THE SOIL DATA OWNER AND/OR PROVIDER (name, direction, country, postal code, website, any other useful information to identify) represented for the purpose of signing this contract by (name, surname, email address)

The DG-JRC and the soil data owner/provider are hereinafter named Parties.

2. Preamble

- Considering the EU Directive 2003/04/EC, the EU Directive 2007/2/EC (the INSPIRE Directive), the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on General Data Protection (GDPR), and their transposition into national laws.
- Considering that under Article 17(8) of Directive 2007/2/EC (INSPIRE) Member States or their public authorities shall enable the institutions and bodies of the Community to gain access to spatial data sets and services under harmonised conditions, and to exchange and use those sets and services, for the purposes of public tasks that may have an impact on the environment.
- Considering that the DG-JRC is an institution or body of the Community.
- Considering that the THE SOIL DATA OWNER is a _____ (choose among 'public authority' or 'third party') following the definition given by the Directive 2007/2/EC (INSPIRE).
- Considering that any charges must be fully compatible with the terms of Article 17(3) of Directive 2007/2/EC and Commission Regulation (EU) No 268/2010.
- Considering that a common structure and terminology of licences can play a role in stimulating the provision of spatial data sets and services under harmonised conditions. Whereas the terms of this licence always must be considered to be in harmony with the Directive 2007/2/EC and its implementing rules"
- Considering that the Directive 2007/2/EC states that "*There is a degree of overlap between the spatial information covered by this Directive and the information covered by Directive 2003/4/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2003 on public access to environmental information. This Directive should be without prejudice to Directive 2003/4/EC*".
- Considering that based on the article 4(2) of the Directives 2003/04/EC and upheld in the article 13(1) of the INSPIRE Directive 2007/2/EC, Member States may refuse a request to provide environmental information if disclosure of the information would adversely affect:

- (a) the confidentiality of the proceedings of public authorities, where such confidentiality is provided for by law;
- (b) international relations, public security or national defence;
- (c) the course of justice, the ability of any person to receive a fair trial or the ability of a public authority to conduct an enquiry of a criminal or disciplinary nature;
- (d) the confidentiality of commercial or industrial information where such confidentiality is provided for by national or Community law to protect a legitimate economic interest, including the public interest in maintaining statistical confidentiality and tax secrecy;
- (e) intellectual property rights;
- (f) the confidentiality of personal data and/or files relating to a natural person where that person has not consented to the disclosure of the information to the public, where such confidentiality is provided for by national or Community law;
- (g) the interests or protection of any person who supplied the information requested on a voluntary basis without being under, or capable of being put under, a legal obligation to do so, unless that person has consented to the release of the information concerned;
- (h) the protection of the environment to which such information relates, such as the location of rare species.

The grounds for refusal mentioned in paragraphs 1 and 2 shall be interpreted in a restrictive way, taking into account for the particular case the public interest served by disclosure. In every particular case, the public interest served by disclosure shall be weighed against the interest served by the refusal. Member States may not, by virtue of paragraph 2(a), (d), (f), (g) and (h), provide for a request to be refused where the request relates to information on emissions into the environment.

- Considering that following the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on General Data Protection (GDPR), « 'personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); and an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person. »
- Considering that point georeferenced soil data are information related to an identifiable location, and that the land of this location can be under private property.
- Considering that georeferenced soil data are recognised as 'personal data under European Directive', in the transposition given by several EU countries in their national legislations. In those countries, abiding by national laws, georeferenced soil data need an authorization to be published online, which must be given by the respective landowners, and the need for such authorization by landowners for the publication online of georeferenced soil data is often explicitly declared in the agreements for soil sampling signed with landowners in several EU countries.
- Considering that elaborated soil maps and other data or knowledge, in whichever format, can be subject to intellectual property rights, owned by the authors of those soil maps and other data or knowledge, and that those intellectual property rights are (or should be) declared in the metadata.

- Considering that elaborated soil maps and other data or knowledge, in whichever format, are published by some institutions under specific licences, which are (or should be) declared in the metadata.
- Considering that elaborated soil maps and other data or knowledge, in whichever format, are shared by some institutions under the recognition of an economic payment, and that the respective fees are (or should be) explicitly declared in the metadata.

The parties have agreed to the following data sharing agreement (Licence) which applies to soil data produced by national soil data providers outside EU funding mechanisms in which data sharing to JRC ESDAC is regulated, and is signed on the basis of the INSPIRE Directive 2007/2/EC.

3. Definitions

Subject: soil data, as described by the metadata (APPENDIX 1).

Anonymised data (or anonymous information): soil data which is not completely visible to the public, by hiding to the public some of the information available (e.g. GDPR sensitive data).

Data owner: Person or institution that has collected and compiled the data, directly or by sub-contracting, and has ownership rights to the data and metadata. The data owner is not necessarily the data provider but can make his/her data available to a data provider for sharing it with the DG - JRC. When "data provider" is mentioned in this agreement, both data provider and data owner are meant.

Data provider: Person or institution providing data and metadata to the DG - JRC under the terms of this License. Ideally, the data provider is identical to the data owner; but a data provider may "only" be providing data to the DG - JRC owned by a different data owner. The data provider either has ownership rights on the data and metadata or the right to reuse them.

Data record: A linear collection of associated data fields (e.g., a results of soil analysis occurring in a sample/site with the associated quantities, methods and abiotic and biotic sample/site variables). Conceptually, this can be thought of as one line in an extended spreadsheet.

Dataset: A collection of associated data records. Minimally, a combination of data record and associated metadata. Conceptually, this can be thought of as a (or multiple) spreadsheet table(s).

Data user: The institution or body of the Community (JRC) that obtains the right to use the Subject under the terms of this data sharing agreement.

Embargo: A time period during which data delivered to the European Commission is not made available to the public. Usually, to allow time for publication or finishing a thesis related to the data.

Metadata: information describing datasets and data services and making it possible to discover, inventory and use them.

Environmental information (based on the Directive 2003/4/EC): any information in written, visual, aural, electronic or any other material form on: on the state of elements of the environment such as air, atmosphere, water, land, wetlands, genetically modified organisms etc.; factors such as noise, emissions and discharges etc.; measures such as policies, legislation, environmental agreements and

others; reports on the implementation of environmental legislation; cost-benefit and other economic analyses; and, the state of human health and safety, including any effects or consequences of the aforementioned.

Public authority (based on the INSPIRE Directive 2007/2/EC):

- a) any government or other public administration, including public advisory bodies, at national, regional or local level;
- b) any natural or legal person performing public administrative functions under national law, including specific duties, activities or services in relation to the environment;
- c) and (c) any natural or legal person having public responsibilities or functions, or providing public services relating to the environment under the control of a body or person falling within a) or b).

Information held by a public authority (based on the Directive 2003/4/EC): environmental information in its possession which has been produced or received by that authority.

Information held for a public authority (based on the Directive 2003/4/EC): environmental information which is physically held by a natural or legal person on behalf of a public authority.

Applicant (based on the Directive 2003/4/EC): natural or legal person that requests environmental information, while the public means one or more legal persons, and in accordance with national legislation or practice, their associations, organizations, or groups.

Environmental officer (based on the Directive 2003/4/EC): person and/or institution which is designated by the Member States to establish and maintain the facilities for the examination of the environmental information required, that is, registers or lists of the environmental information held by public authorities or information points, with clear indications of where such information can be found.

Third party (based on the Directive 2003/4/EC): Any natural or legal person other than a public authority.

4. Grant

The soil data owner/provider grants to the data user a non-exclusive and non-transferable agreement to use the subject according to the terms of Directive 2007/2/EC (INSPIRE) and Commission Regulation (EU) No 268/2010 of 29 March 2010 (the Regulation).

4.1 Use

The Parties are invited to use the sharing rules check-list (APPENDIX 2).

Use for any purpose other than permitted by this agreement is expressly prohibited without the prior written permission of the soil data owner/provider, who in its sole discretion may deny such permission or claim a separate additional charge for it.

4.2 Access and delivery

The Data owner/provider shall ensure that DG-JRC Data user gets access to the Subject in a timely and efficient manner, according to the terms of this agreement. The Data owner/provider undertakes to ensure that independent of the provisions agreed to for access, the DG-JRC can get access to the Subject without delay in major emergencies with an impact on the environment.

4.3 Liability

The Subject is provided on “as is” basis, without warranty of any kind, either expressed or implied, except as otherwise provided in this agreement. No oral or written advice given by the data owner/provider or its dealers, distributors, agents or employees creates a warranty or in any way increases data owner/provider’s liability. Neither of the Parties shall be liable for any indirect damage. The data owner/provider shall not be liable for any damage arising out of reliance upon, use or inability to use the Subject. The data owner/provider shall not be liable for any harm that may be caused by the transmission of a computer virus, worm or other such computer program. This clause does not exclude liability for the data owner/provider where this is prescribed by national law. The data owner/provider will not be liable for any lack of service caused by the network of the Data user, except as expressly provided in this agreement.

4.4 Processing of personal data

Some personal data of the Parties may be requested in order to sign the present agreement. The Parties, aware of the consequences for the infringement of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR), will not share those data outside the present agreement. Disclosure to third parties will not occur.

4.5 Assignment, sub-licensing

This agreement may not be assigned. DG-JRC has no rights to sub-license the Subject.

4.6 Sub-contracting

Where DG-JRC contracts work which requires use of the Subject to another entity, the Subject may be supplied under the following conditions: • The contractor shall be bound by the same obligations as the DG-JRC under this agreement; • The contractor shall not be given the power to grant rights to the Subject;

4.7 Warranties

The Data owner/provider warrants to the DG-JRC that to the best of its knowledge it has the authority and power to grant the rights granted under this agreement, has no reason to believe that the use of the Subject could infringe any other entity’s rights and is not aware of any claim alleging that such infringement exists. The Data owner/provider does not warrant that the Subject will meet the requirements of the DG-JRC, unless this is stated specifically or follows from national law. Neither does the Data owner/provider warrant that its operation will be uninterrupted or error free. Except as expressly provided in this agreement, there are no conditions, warranties or other terms binding on the Data owner/provider with respect to the actions contemplated hereunder. Any condition, warranty or other term in this regard which might otherwise be implied or incorporated into this agreement, whether by statute, common law or otherwise, is, insofar as it is lawful to do so, hereby excluded.

4.8 Security

DG-JRC shall maintain adequate security measures to protect the integrity and confidentiality of the Subject. The Data user shall notify the Data owner/provider of any breach or suspected breach of such security measures.

4.9 Force majeure

No Party shall be liable for failures or have the right to terminate this agreement for any delay or failure in performance under this agreement if such delay or failure is caused by force majeure. The non-performing Party shall inform the other Party in writing as soon as is practicable about the force majeure circumstances specifying the nature and extent of the circumstances.

The non-performing party has no liability in respect of the performance of such of its obligations as are prevented by the force majeure events during the continuation of such events, and for such time after they cease as is necessary for that party, using all reasonable endeavours, to commence its affected operations in order for it to perform its obligations.

Force majeure shall mean any cause preventing a party from performing any or all of its obligations which arises from or is attributable to acts, events, omissions or accidents beyond the reasonable control of the party so prevented including without limitation strikes, lock-outs or other industrial disputes (whether involving the workforce of the party so prevented or of any other party), act of God, war, riot, civil commotion, act of terrorism, malicious damage, compliance with any law or governmental order, rule, regulation or direction, accident, breakdown of plant or machinery, fire, flood or storm.

4.10 Conflict resolution

In the event of any dispute over the agreement, that may arise between the parties regarding the validity, effectiveness, interpretation and execution of this agreements, of the subsequent agreements and in any case connected to it, and/or the correct use of the data in question, the parties shall attempt to solve the issue by negotiations. Either Party may suspend the agreement until the dispute is resolved. In the event of the said issues not being solved within 3 months from the start of the negotiations, the parties may bring the issue to the applicable court of law. Any dispute unsolved within the 3 months will be defined in compliance with current legislation in the State of residence of the data owner and must be preceded, under penalty of inadmissibility of the request, by the request for an opinion, mandatory, non-binding, to the European Data Protection Supervisor.

4.11 Applicable law and jurisdiction

Any dispute rising that cannot be solved by negotiation is to be handled as a dispute under the law of [insert relevant jurisdiction].

4.12 Termination

This license can be terminated by the Parties. Termination cannot be without a reasonable cause. If there is a material breach of contract, the agreement can be terminated with immediate effect. [Option 1: This agreement can be terminated by the Parties with 60 days written notice by registered mail. Option 2: This agreement will terminate at the end of the agreement period as specified in Schedule 13. Option 3: This service can be changed or terminated at any time by the service provider, on such notice that is reasonable in the circumstances. Option 4: This service can be terminated by the provider with [insert the number of days] days written notice. Option 5: In the event of this service being changed by the service provider, the Licensee is entitled to terminate this agreement from that the same time.

5. APPENDIX 1 - Description of the soil data shared (metadata)

(a) conformity of spatial data sets with the implementing rules provided for in Article 7(1) of the INSPIRE DIRECTIVE 2007/2/EC

(b) the quality and validity of spatial data sets;

(c) the public authorities (eventually) responsible for the establishment, management, maintenance and distribution of spatial data sets and services;

(d) the conditions applying to access to, and use of, spatial data sets and services and, where applicable, corresponding fees, and limitations on public access and the reasons for such limitations, in accordance with Article 13 of the INSPIRE DIRECTIVE 2007/2/EC are reported in the Article 3 of the present agreement on data sharing rules.

(e) any other metadata, not foreseen by the Article 5 of the INSPIRE DIRECTIVE 2007/2/EC, which the data provider considers essential to be included

6. APPENDIX 2 - Soil data sharing rules

DG-JRC can publish, in its metadata repositories, the metadata of the data shared with the present agreement, explicitly declaring the exceptions or limitations to public data access as declared by the soil data owner/provider. The soil data owner/provider declares that the following exceptions or limitations to public data access applies to the soil data shared with DG-JRC with the present agreement (empty checkboxes mean that the exclusions or limitations are NOT requested).

The following license

_____ applies to the soil data shared as described in APPENDIX 1.

The soil data cannot be shared online nor with third parties without the authorization of the soil data owner

The soil data can be shared online and/or with third parties after anonymization, that is, given that the following data fields are not made publicly available (= anonymized):

- The soil data coordinates shared with DG-JRC could be used by DG-JRC for resampling at the exact locations only under the permission by the respective landowners.
- The soil data can be used by DG-JRC for further elaborations, given that the Public Authority responsible to perform public administrative functions in relation to soil under national law or having public responsibilities or functions in relation to soil, is kept informed and duly involved in the activity.
- The soil data can be shared online and/or with third parties given that the soil data owner and/or provider is recognized by using the following citation

- The soil data is shared with DG-JRC given that the following economic payment to the soil data owner and/or provider is recognized.

7. Privacy and security statement

Except for the names of the data providers/owners/authors, the personal data of data providers (including e-mail addresses, telephone numbers, postal addresses, etc.) will never be made accessible to the public in any form nor given to requesting individuals without prior approval by the data provider. The personal data of landowners are never published online, unless the landowners have given expressed authorization.

Location, date

Data owner

Location, date

DG-JRC

